

Phylogenetics: back to basics

1 July 2024

11am - 3pm AEST/ 10:30 - 2:30pm ACST/ 9am - 1pm AWST

Schedule

*Timings are approximate and subject to change. ([Check the start time in your timezone](#))

Time	Activity	Who?
11.00 AEST	Welcome and housekeeping	Melissa
11.10 AEST	Why Phylogenetics and tree anatomy Basic tree building methodology and Multiple sequence alignment EXERCISE: Viewing data and sequence alignment with MAFFT Building trees from distances EXERCISE: Build a Neighbour-Joining Tree with FastTree EXERCISE: Estimating a Maximum Likelihood tree with IQTree	Michael C
Approx 12:45	BREAK (15 mins)	
1.00 AEST	Estimating trees from alignments Phylogenetic networks in SplitsTree EXERCISE: Phylogenetic networks	Michael C
2.50 AEST	Summary of workshop	Michael C
2.55 AEST	Wrap up and feedback survey	Melissa
3.00 AEST	End of Workshop	